

SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY: KEY BARRIERS

Dr Shaji Thomas, Assistant Professor, Pavanatma College, Murickassey

ABSTRACT:

Sustainable waste management plays a crucial role in maintaining a healthy environment. However, factors such as rapid population growth, increasing waste generation, the complexity of solid waste, inadequate regulation enforcement, inefficiencies in disposal methods, and limited financial and infrastructural resources contribute to ineffective waste management in many countries. The study aims to determine barriers to waste management in food industries and find the knowledge of respondents about various laws and regulations related to waste management and control. The findings of this study contribute to understanding the barriers to solid waste management in the food industries in Idukki districts and provide insights for policymakers and practitioners to develop effective and sustainable waste management strategies for the future world.

Key Words: Environment Strategies, Sustainable, Waste Management

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY :

Solid waste created by human activities is a source of concern, particularly in India's major cities, and the problem is expected to rise as urbanisation and economic development continue. During the past few centuries, unprecedented and powerful changes have transformed the world's economic landscape. One of the most important changes among them is 'Industrialisation'. The Industrial Revolution in the 18th century not only provided new inventions and technology for mass production but also led the European powers to colonise many nations for new markets and raw materials. It creates food manufacturing and chain facilities, generating employment and export earnings. However, at the same time, food industries play a significant role in production and generate solid waste. This situation creates serious environmental problems and social issues in entire sectors. Therefore, sustainable waste management practices are necessary for a healthy world. Moreover, sustainable and effective waste management practices align with circular economy principles by promoting recycling and reuse, conserving resources and reducing environmental impacts (Hernández & Romero, 2018).

Waste management must become more sophisticated as society moves towards a more sustainable future. The rigidity and short-term focus of conventional reductionist methods make them insufficient, underscoring the need for more flexible and progressive approaches. Seadon, J K. (2010). Singh (2015) drew attention to the achievements made by certain Indian towns in modernising their waste management systems and implementing new sanitation and waste management policies, rules, and infrastructure. Song et al. (2023) investigated how better urban waste management could save energy, resources, and the environment. The findings suggest managing urban waste is crucial to a region's sustainability.

India now produces the most garbage globally, which is expected to increase by 2050 unless fast action is taken. Industrial, mining, municipal, agricultural, and other operations generate significant amounts of solid waste yearly Ebekozi et al., (2022). Population growth, fast industrialisation, urbanisation, and economic growth have all contributed to a significant increase in solid waste. The volume of solid waste generated in Indian cities has dramatically increased, from 6 million tonnes in 1947 to 48 million tonnes in 1997, showing an annual growth rate of 4.25 percent. Projections indicate that this figure could reach 300 million tons by 2047 (CPCB, 1998). Solid waste management is a pressing global challenge, and India is no exception. With a population surpassing 1.3 billion, the country produces approximately 62 million tonnes of solid waste yearly, ranking as the world's third-largest waste generator (Sharma et al., 2021).

Mainu, S., (2023). revealed that significant gaps and obstacles still hinder effective waste management in the country. They identified infrastructure and resource constraints, institutional and

governance issues, and environmental and social impacts as significant challenges. (Agarwal et al., 2015) identified waste management difficulties such as inadequate collection and segregation at the source, waste disposal, land scarcity, a lack of knowledge, etc. Tchobanoglaus, G. et al. (1993) stated that the integrated practice of managing solid waste has developed in response to the regulations established to instrument various techniques.

Dhamija, U.(2006). Outlined the role of authorities in correctly disposing of waste, referring to urban solid waste as municipal solid waste since the local government, or municipality, is thought to be in the most significant position to collect and dispose of it because of its proximity to the waste producing location. Gour, A. (2022) concluded that in order to implement solid waste management in developing countries adequately, prompt action is required for the management of data, education, training, planning, monitoring, strict policy changes with robust legislation, the building of a reliable regulatory system, proper and practical management of all waste streams, public awareness, and most suitable housekeeping practices.

Garcia & Turner (2018) noted that many countries have implemented comprehensive waste management regulations covering waste collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal. These regulations typically establish guidelines for waste segregation, recycling targets, landfill restrictions, and adopting waste-to-energy technologies. Shrestha & Tanaka (2017) emphasized investing in advanced waste management technologies to enhance waste collection, sorting, recycling, and treatment processes. Innovations like artificial intelligence, robotics, and advanced sorting techniques can significantly improve resource recovery and waste-handling efficiency.

The European Commission (2020) advocates for decentralized waste management models, including community-based composting and local waste-to-energy facilities. These approaches can help lower transportation costs and reduce the environmental impact associated with waste collection and disposal. The principles of "Reduce, Reuse, and Refuse" encourage consumers to adopt sustainable choices while minimizing waste generation. Furthermore, the circular economy model promotes a closed-loop system, ensuring that products are designed for durability, repairability, recyclability, and reusability, ultimately reducing their environmental impact. (Seadon, 2010; Gören, 2014; Elsaid & Aghezzaf, 2015).

Khosravani et al. (2023) outlined five key objectives of sustainable waste management that align with the Sustainable Development Goals. These include institutional, technical, infrastructural, environmental, economic, and cultural-social goals, which are fundamental pillars for practical waste management strategies. Past technical advancements did not reduce the rate of resource use, raising concerns that increasing efficiency may not be the ultimate solution to enabling a happy life for everybody within the planet's borders. Effective systems should be designed to address human requirements, followed by optimisation for environmental efficiency (Hu et al., 2017). Applying innovations can overcome some difficulties with waste management and provide additional benefits.

Awasthi, A.K. (2001). Ghosh (2016) highlights that while advanced waste management technologies provide significant benefits, technical and logistical challenges often hinder implementation. The need for specialised infrastructure and a skilled workforce makes deploying and operating these technologies difficult. Rani & Yendluri, (2024) emphasized that promoting a culture of sustainability requires effective education and communication initiatives. These efforts are vital in raising public awareness about the importance of recycling, proper waste segregation, and waste reduction.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the barriers to implementing waste management techniques in food industries
2. To study respondents' knowledge about the various laws and government regulations on waste management and control.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The methodology discusses the available research methods suitable for the study and their

applicability. The primary data collection process was conducted by administering a structured questionnaire to respondents. Additionally, secondary data were sourced from many reputable outlets, including journals, textbooks, articles, and websites. The sample size determination is set at 50 participants; then, the business units are classified into four heads: fruits and vegetables, Milk Products, Packed foods and soft drinks, Meat and Fish, and Others. Data is collected from samples using a structured questionnaire. The sampling method chosen was 'Stratified sampling'. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to analyze and draw inferences from the data collected from the respondents. The selected research design was descriptive research.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY:

The General profile of the respondents is shown in Table 3.1

Table3. 1

General Profile of the respondents

Profile of the respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Nature of the Unit		
Fruits & Vegetables	15	30
Packed Foods & Soft drinks	20	40
Meat & Fish	10	20
Others	5	10
Ownership of the Unit		
Sole Proprietorship	37	74
Partnership	11	22
Others	2	4
Year of Establishment		
Before 2000	10	20
2000-2005	20	40
2005-2010	5	10
After 2010	15	30
Interest in implementing waste management technology in units		
Highly Interested	9	18
Interested	41	82
Not Interested	0	0
Existence of Waste Disposal System in units		
Yes	40	80
No	10	20

Modes of Waste Disposal		
Self- Disposal	38	76
Municipal Disposal	7	14
Others	5	10
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

Table 4.1 presents the respondents' profiles. A significant share (40%) belongs to the "Packed Foods & Soft Drinks" category. Most sample units operate as sole proprietorships, with the majority established between 2000 and 2005. Notably, 82% of respondents were strongly willing to implement technology in their units, while none reported being "Not Interested." Additionally, 80% of the sample units have a waste disposal system, whereas 20% do not. Among those with disposal systems, 76% practice self-disposal, 14% rely on municipal waste management, and 10% use alternative methods.

3.2 Barriers for implementing waste management techniques

The respondents were asked various questions on the five-point Likert scale to find the barriers to implementing waste management techniques in their business. Barriers to implementing waste management techniques are shown in Table 3. 2

Table 3.2

Barriers for implementing waste management technique

Barriers	Mean Percentage score (%)	Rnak
Information barriers	22	2
Economic barriers	33	1
Technological barriers	18	3
Human Resource barriers	15	4
Regulatory barriers	10	5
Others	2	6

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

Table 3.2 highlights the barriers to implementing waste management techniques. Most respondents (33%) identified economic barriers as the primary challenge, followed by information, technological, human resource, and regulatory barriers for the second, third, fourth, and fifth positions. These factors collectively hinder the effective adoption of waste management practices.

3.3 Respondents' awareness about the Environmental Acts and rules

The respondents were asked various questions on the five-point Likert scale to determine their awareness of various environmental Acts and rules. The respondents' awareness of various Environmental Acts and rules is shown in Table 3. 2

Table 3.3

Respondents' awareness about the Environmental Acts and rules

Laws	Mean Percentage score (%)
Water (Prevention & Control of Pollution) Act 1974	18

Air(Prevention & Control of Pollution) Act 1981	14
Environmental (Protection) Act 1986	42
Plastic Waste (Management & Handling) Rules 2011	13
Others Environmental laws	13

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

Table 3.3 presents respondents' awareness of various environmental laws. The majority of respondents were unaware of these regulations. Only 42% were familiar with the Environmental (Protection) Act, 18% knew about the Water (Prevention & Control of Pollution) Act, and 14% were aware of the Air (Prevention & Control of Pollution) Act. In short, most respondents are unaware of various Environmental Protection Acts and laws.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS OF THE STUDY:

The study was conducted to study the waste management system in food industries in Idukki district. For this purpose, a survey was conducted among 50 units. Their response has been analyzed in the previous chapter. This section enumerates the important findings and suggestions

Findings of the study:

The major findings of the study are listed below-

- Most respondents fall into the categories of Packed Foods and soft drinks, and the majority of the respondents were sole proprietorships.
- Major units were established between the years 2000 and 2005.
- 82% of respondents were highly interested in implementing waste management technology in their units.
- 80 % of the sample respondents adopt a waste disposal system in their units, and 20% of respondents have no waste disposal system.
- 76% adopt self-disposal for waste disposal.
- Most respondents had incurred Rs.1000 to Rs 5000 per month for waste disposal (53%).
- Economic barrier was the main barrier for respondents to adopt waste management technology
- Most of the respondents were not aware of various Environmental protection Acts and laws

Suggestions of the study:

1. People are not ready to implement waste disposal systems in their units for many reasons. Steps must be taken to acquire people's interest in this area.
2. Open dumping is not a suitable method for waste disposal. Adoption of other sources should be encouraged. Municipalities and Panchayats are more concentrated on waste disposal by adopting scientific and environment-friendly methods.
3. The government must educate the public about the need for effective environmental acts and rules. Seminars and workshops can be conducted to educate people more about various environmental acts and rules and effective waste disposal.
4. Monetary and other incentives from government authorities help encourage the public to be involved in waste management.
5. Compliments and gifts can be given to those who adopt effective waste management systems in their units.

CONCLUSION:

Effective waste management is necessary for sustainable development in the modern business world. Ineffective waste management creates many problems for business units, such as high production costs, a bad image among the public, loss of goodwill, legal action from authorities, etc., so a study

in waste management and disposal is critical. It also intends to give some suggestions to business units on how to move forward in this area. Environment-friendly operations are suitable for any business to reach the public's hearts. Proper waste management practices help contribute to environment-friendly operations and meet a business's corporate social responsibility.

Effective waste management in the food industry requires proactive efforts from business units supported by government initiatives. Businesses should adopt sustainable waste disposal methods, while authorities play a crucial role in eliminating barriers to implementation. Public awareness is equally important governments must educate citizens about environmental laws, regulations, and associated penalties. Organizing seminars and workshops can further enhance awareness and encourage responsible waste disposal practices. Ultimately, implementing environmentally friendly and cost-effective waste management solutions benefits businesses and society, fostering a cleaner and more sustainable future.

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